

Evaluation Of Antidiarrheal Activity of a Prebiotic Formulation Containing (Gum Acacia, Gir Cow Ghee & Sugar) On Rat Model

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ABSTRACT

The current work examines the in-vivo antidiarrheal effects of a prebiotic formulation containing gum acacia, Gir cow ghee, and sugar in a castor oil-induced diarrhea model with Sprague Dawley rats. Diarrhea was produced using castor oil (2 mL/kg), and the formulation's protective effects were assessed at two dose levels and compared to the conventional medicine loperamide (5 mg/kg). The following parameters were evaluated: beginning of diarrhea, total number of fecal outputs, wet feces, and percentage inhibition of diarrhea. The prebiotic formulation dramatically reduced diarrhea frequency and improved stool consistency in treated groups, with the high-dose group demonstrating the greatest inhibition. The data indicate that the synergistic impact of gum acacia (prebiotic fiber), Gir bovine ghee (a source of SCFAs, particularly butyrate), and glucose (which improves water-electrolyte absorption) helps to restore intestinal balance and prevent castor-oil-induced diarrhea. This study supports the use of natural, food-grade prebiotic compounds as a safe and effective antidiarrheal medication.

Keywords: Prebiotic formulation; Gum acacia; Gir cow ghee; Castor oil-induced diarrhea; Antidiarrheal activity; Sprague Dawley rats; Short-chain fatty acids; Butyrate; Loperamide; Gut microbiota.

INTRODUCTION

A common gastrointestinal ailment brought on by infections, poisons, or inflammatory diseases is diarrhea.^[1] An estimated 1.8 million people die each year from dehydration brought on by diarrhea.^[2] When the colon's ability to absorb fluids is inadequate, such as when the colon is injured or irritated, diarrhea results.^[3] It is generally defined as three or more loose or watery stools within a 24-hour period, or a decrease in the consistency of the stool from that which is normal for the patient.^[4]

MOA: These pathogens are spread through the fecal-oral pathway, in which an infected person or animal excretes the pathogens from their digestive tract and consumes them. Water moves into the lumen in an effort to restore the proper ion concentrations when the intestinal epithelium's ability to absorb and secrete ions and solutes is compromised, resulting in diarrhea.^[5]

Symptoms: may include thirst, restlessness or irritability, loss of skin elasticity, loose or watery stools, stomach pain, vomiting, blood or mucus in stool.^[6]

Diarrhea can be of numerous types:

1) Osmotic Diarrhea: It is caused by osmotically active, poorly absorbed solutes that obstruct regular absorption of water and electrolytes in the gut lumen.

2) Motility-related Diarrhea: Loose, watery stools are the result of your intestines moving food and waste too quickly (hypermotility), which leaves your body with little opportunity to absorb water and electrolytes.

3) Secretory Diarrhea: This kind of diarrhea results in watery stools that persist even while fasting because the intestinal lining actively secretes too much water and electrolytes (such as salt and

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chloride) into the gut, overriding the colon's capacity to absorb them.

4) Inflammatory Diarrhea: It occurs when the lining of colon (large intestine) becomes inflamed, commonly due to infections or chronic illnesses like Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD – Crohn's or Ulcerative Colitis).^[7]

Gibson and Roberfroid first mentioned **Prebiotics** in the scientific press in 1995.^[8] Prebiotics improve gut health by feeding gut microorganisms. It encourages gut microorganisms to proliferate and engage in advantageous activities. It is described as materials that have undergone selective fermentation, leading to certain alterations, particularly in the composition of the GIT microbiota, which have an impact on the host's health.^[9]

Introduction to Prebiotic Formulation

Gum Arabic (GA), a soluble fiber produced from *Acacia senegal*, has prebiotic characteristics, increases microbial fermentation, boosts SCFA synthesis, and regulates intestinal barrier function. It is a soluble fiber with mild emulsifying qualities that could increase the microvillus membrane's accessibility to electrolytes and related fluids.^[10] Extra effort showed that GA does not work through sodium-dependent processes and improved absorption of the solutes carried by diffusion.^[11] It shows a prebiotic effect which enhances gut microbiota balance. It forms a protective mucosal layer, reducing irritation.^[10]

Gir cow ghee, which is rich in butyrate and other short-chain fatty acids, has anti-inflammatory properties and promotes intestinal healing. Because to its natural antioxidant content and low moisture level, it has a fairly stable shelf life. Since ancient times, ghee and ayurveda have had a very intimate relationship.^[12] According to Kumar et al., butyric acid, a short-chain fatty acid that gives food a unique flavour and aids in digestion, is present in ghee in contrast to other oils.^[13] According to research, butyric acid production provides sufficient support for the gut's killer T cell generation, leading to a robust immune system.^[14]

The **sugar** used in the formulation of this suspension is glucose sugar. Glucose facilitates the absorption of sodium and water across the intestinal wall, helping to replace fluids and electrolytes loss during diarrhea and preventing dehydration.^[15]

The current study assesses the antidiarrheal efficacy of a new prebiotic solution including gum acacia, Gir cow ghee, and sugar in rats with experimentally induced diarrhea. The theory is that this synergistic formulation will reduce diarrhea frequency by boosting gut microbial balance, mucosal integrity, and fluid absorption.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Materials:

- Gum Acacia – Prebiotic Soluble Fiber
- Gir Cow Ghee – Source of SCFAs (especially butyric acid)
- Sugar (Glucose) – Supports Water-electrolyte balance
- Castor oil – Diarrhea inducing agent (2 ml/kg)
- Standard Drug – Loperamide (5 mg/kg)
- Experimental Animals – Sprague Dawley Rats (200-350gm)
- Solid Plastic Cages
- Oral Feeding Needles

All the chemicals and materials were of analytical grade.

2.2 Experimental Animals:

Sprague Dawley (SD) Rats of both sexes, aged 3-5 months were kept at Sigma Institute of Clinical Research and Administration Pvt. Ltd. for acclimatization for 6 days, prior to experimentation. Rats were maintained at room temperature of 22°C ($\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$) and relative humidity between 30 & 70%. Twelve-hour light and dark cycle were maintained with automatic light system. With the exception of

times specified by protocol, animals were permitted unrestricted access to purified water and standard diet followed. All the experimental procedures were carried out as per CPCSEA guidelines and approved by ethical committee. (Approval No.: E/IAEC/SICRA/2190/2025) ^[16]

2.3 Grouping of Animals:

In castor oil-induced and E. coli-induced diarrhea models, rats were randomly divided into 5 groups (n=5)

Group 1: It is known as a Normal Control Group. It received saline water.

Group 2: It is known as Negative Control Group. It shows an induction of diarrhea in a rat with two (castor oil & E. coli) induction models of diarrhea.

Group 3: It is known as a Standard Treatment Group. It received a standard drug (loperamide) at a dose of (5mg/kg) prior from study and 1h after gives castor oil & e. coli per oral route (p.o.) and finding observations up to 4 hours.

Group 4: It is known as a Test Treatment Group (Low Dose). It received a Prebiotic Formulation at a dose of (1ml) prior from study and 1h after gives castor oil & e. coli p.o. and finding observations up to 4 hours.

Group 5: It is known as a Test Treatment Group (High Dose). It received a Prebiotic Formulation at a dose of (2ml) prior from study and 1h after gives castor oil & e. coli p.o. and finding observations up to 4 hours. ^[16]

2.4 Induction of Diarrhea:

It is carried out by two methods-

- Castor oil-induced Diarrhea
- E-coli induced Diarrhea

A) Castor oil-induced Diarrhea: Rats with castor oil-induced diarrhea are frequently used as models in studies to examine the processes behind diarrhea to evaluate possible anti-diarrheal medications. Castor oil causes watery diarrhea within a few hours after oral administration because it increases fluid output and enhances intestinal motility. ^[17] This model is very helpful for researching the function of prostaglandins and nitric oxide in diarrhea, as well as the effectiveness of different drugs or natural cures. Rats given castor oil (2 ml/kg orally) had diarrhea 1–7 hours after the challenge, which was linked to significant harm to the mucosa of the duodenum and the jejunum. Acid phosphatase was released into the intestinal lumen along with the lesion, indicating cellular damage. ^[18]

Fig.1 Flowchart for Mechanism of Action of Castor oil-induced Diarrhea^[19]

B) E-coli induced Diarrhea: The fecal-oral route is the mode of transmission. The ileal mucosa can be colonized by the bacteria thanks to pili (fimbriae). Watery diarrhea is caused by cytotoxic enterotoxins, which are encoded on plasmid or bacteriophage DNA.^[20] The presence of either of these factors causes

a host inflammatory response with an influx of lymphocytes and consequent dysentery. Plasmid-encoded invasion factors allow penetration of the mucosa, whereas cytotoxic enterotoxins carried by plasmids or bacteriophages cause tissue destruction.^[21]

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

3.1 Preparation of Prebiotic Formulation:

Table 1: Preparation of Prebiotic Formulation

Ingredients	Purpose	Concentration (%w/v)	Quantity for 100 ml
Gum Acacia	Prebiotic agent/ Suspending agent	3-5%	3-5g
Gir cow ghee	Active lipid component	3-5%	3-5g
Sugar	Sweetener, Stabilizer & Fermentation	8-10%	8-10g
Distilled water	Vehicle for emulsion	q.s. to 100ml	Up to 100 ml

3.2 Procedure for Preparation of Prebiotic Formulation:

Weigh 3-5gm of Gum Acacia and gradually add it to 100 ml warm distilled water with continuous stirring to form a mucilage. Let it hydrate for few minutes to form a uniform suspension. Weigh 3-5gm of Gir Cow Ghee and Melt it at 40-50°C. Slowly add the molten ghee into the gum acacia mucilage while stirring continuously to form an emulsion. Weigh 8-10gm of sugar and dissolve it in a small amount of warm water. Add this sugar solution to the suspension to enhance palatability and stability. Mix all the components thoroughly using a magnetic stirrer for 10-15 minutes for proper homogenization. Adjust the final volume up to 100ml with distilled water. Store the emulsion in an amber glass bottle at 4-8°C. Shake well before use.

3.3 Preparation of E. coli Bacteria Solution:

Enterotoxigenic Escherichia coli (ETEC) bacteria solution prepared in physiologic saline at the concentration of 1.5 mg/ml corresponding to 5.10⁹ CFU/ml, incubated for 1 h at 37°C before oral administration to rats at the dose of 30 mg/kg in an administration volume of 20 ml/kg.^[22]

3.4 Procedure for castor oil-induced Diarrhea model:

All the animals housed under a standard laboratory condition at a room temperature following 12h light: dark cycle. Standard diet and water were provided constantly. Fasten the rats 18 hours before starting of an experimental procedure. Group 1 receiving vehicle (saline water) via oral gavage. Group 2 receives castor oil to induce the diarrhea in rats at a dose of 2ml/kg. Group 3 receives a standard drug (loperamide) at a dose of 5ml/kg 1hour after giving of castor oil for inducing diarrhea. Group 4&5 receives a test drug at different concentration of 1ml&2ml respectively as a low dose and high dose 1hour after giving of castor oil. Note the parameters such as Onset of feces, Number of Diarrheal Feces, Weight of feses, Zone of inhibition, etc. Finding out the final conclusion by comparing between the Negative Control Group (Group 2), Standard Treatment Group (Group 3) and Test Treatment Groups (Group 4&5). Note down the parameters for a time period of 4 hours.

3.5 Procedure for E-coli induced Diarrhea Model:

Receive E. coli strains on nutrient agar overnight at 37°C. Inoculate a colony into nutrient broth and incubate for 18-24 hour at 37°C with shaking. Adjust the bacterial suspension to ~10⁹ CFU/mL using OD

measurement at 600nm. Fasten the rats for 18 hours before starting of an experimental procedure. Group 1 receiving vehicle (saline water) via oral gavage. Group 2 receives e.coli suspension to induce the diarrhea in rats at a dose of 30mg/kg. Group 3 receives a standard drug (loperamide) at a dose of 5ml/kg 1hour after giving of ecoli suspension (1ml) for inducing diarrhea. Group 4&5 receives a test drug at different concentration of 1ml&2ml respectively as a low dose and high dose 1hour after giving of ecoli suspension. Note the parameters such as Onset of feces, Number of Diarrheal Feces, Weight of feses, Zone of inhibition, etc. Finding out the final conclusion by comparing between the Negative Control Group (Group 2), Standard Treatment Group (Group 3) and Test Treatment Groups (Group 4&5). Note down the parameters for a time period of 4-6 hours.

4. EVALUATION PARAMETERS

4.1 Onset of Diarrhea: In rats given castor oil, the average time for the beginning of diarrhea was known as an onset time of diarrhea. The symptoms of acute diarrhea, which lasts less than 14 days, generally appear 12 hours to a few days after exposure and go away in 3 to 7 days.

4.2 Number of Diarrheal Fecals: The number of diarrheal feces was significantly altered among different experimental groups, indicating the effectiveness of the prebiotic formulation in controlling diarrhea induced by castor oil. The number of diarrheal feces should be calculated by observation.

The Percentage inhibition of diarrhea was calculated as:

$$\text{Percentage Inhibition} = [A-B/A] \times 100$$

A- Mean number of diarrhoeal faeces caused by castor oil administration

B- Mean number of diarrhoeal faeces observed after treatment

4.3 Weight of Diarrheal Feces: The weight of diarrheal feces is a critical parameter in evaluating the

severity of diarrhea and the effectiveness of an antidiarrheal agent. In this study, it served as a quantitative measure of fluid loss and gastrointestinal motility following castor oil administration in rats.

4.4 Fecal Water Content: Fecal water content is a crucial parameter in evaluating the severity of diarrhea and the effectiveness of antidiarrheal agents. In the present study, the fecal water content was significantly elevated in the negative control group indicating severe diarrhea characterized by watery stools.

$$\text{Fecal Water Content (\%)} = \frac{\{\text{Wet Weight}\} - \{\text{Dry Weight}\}}{\{\text{Wet Weight}\}} \times 100$$

4.5 Stool Shape: The shape and consistency of stools were monitored across all experimental groups to evaluate the severity of diarrhea and the therapeutic efficacy of the prebiotic formulation. The following stool shape categories were used for assessment:

- 1. Watery or Semi-liquid stools:** Indicative of severe diarrhea, commonly observed in the negative control group. This type of stool lacks form and suggests increased intestinal motility and fluid secretion.
- 2. Soft, unformed stools:** Represents the moderate diarrhea. These stools retain partial shape but are not fully formed, indicating partial improvement or a less severe diarrheal state.
- 3. Well-formed pellets:** Considered as normal healthy stools. Presence of such stools suggests effective suppression of diarrhea and restoration of normal gut motility and fluid absorption. [23,24]

5. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data was analysed using SPSS version 26.0. All grouped data were statistically analysed, and the significance of different treatments was ascertained using Tukey's HSD post hoc test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results of the study were presented in text, tables as a mean plus or minus standard error of the mean (SEM). The results were also deemed statistically significant at a p-value of 0.05.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Castor oil-induced Diarrhea:

Table 2: Effect of Prebiotic Formulation on Castor oil induced diarrhea in rat

Groups	Onset time of diarrhea (mins.)	Number of diarrheal faeces	Weight of diarrheal faeces (gm)	Percentage inhibition of defecation
Normal Control Group	-	No. of feces =4	Weight of feces =3.56gm	NA
Negative Control Group	42.4±3.97	7.2±0.83	9.7±0.82***	NA
Standard Treatment Group (5mg/kg, p.o.)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	100
Test Treatment Group (Low Dose) (1ml, p.o.)	152±5.56	2.4±0.54	2.51±0.49	66.66
Test Treatment Group (High Dose) (2ml, p.o.)	210.5±0.70	1.0±0.00	1.18±0.08	86.11

NA- Not Applicable. Data was represented as mean±SD. The significance difference at $p < 0.05$. ***-more significant group

6.2 E-coli induced Diarrhea:

Table 3: Effect of Prebiotic Formulation on E. coli induced diarrhea in rat

Groups	Onset time of diarrhea (h)	Number of diarrheal faeces	Weight of diarrheal faeces (gm)	Percentage inhibition of defecation
Normal Control Group	-	No. of feces =5	Weight of feces =4.36gm	NA
Negative Control Group	2.0±0.3	8.6±0.9	10.7±0.92***	NA
Standard Treatment Group (5mg/kg, p.o.)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	100
Test Treatment Group (Low Dose) (1ml, p.o.)	3.5±0.4	3.5±0.7	4.3±0.4	59.30
Test Treatment Group (High Dose) (2ml, p.o.)	4.2±0.3	1.9±0.4	2.3±0.3	77.90

NA- Not Applicable. Data was represented as mean±SD. The significance difference at $p < 0.05$. ***-more significant group

Table 4: Evaluation Parameters for both castor oil and E. coli induced diarrhea models

Groups	Stool Stickiness	Stool Shape	Presence of Mucus or Blood	Fecal Water Content (%)	Stool Images
Normal Control Group	Absent	Well-formed pellets	Absent	10.2	
	Present		Absent	82.4	

Negative Control Group					
Standard Treatment Group (5mg/kg,p.o.)	-	-	-	-	-
Test Treatment Group (Low Dose) (1ml, p*.o.)	Slightly Sticky	Soft stools but nearly formed	Absent	44.4	
Test Treatment Group (High Dose) (2ml, p.o.)	Absent	Well-formed pellets	Absent	15.4	

Table 5: Stool Shapes observed in different treatment groups for both castor oil as well as e-coli induced diarrhea models

Group	Time Post-Castor Oil	Observed Stool Shape
Normal Control	Entire Period	Well-formed pellets
Negative Control (Castor oil)	4 hours	Watery, Semi-liquid stools
Standard Control (Loperamide)	1-4 hours	No stools formed
Test Treatment Low Dose (1ml)	1-4 hours	Soft stools, nearly formed stools
Test Treatment High Dose (2ml)	1-4 hours	Well-formed pellets

6.3 Antimicrobial Test of Prebiotic Formulation:

Fig 3. Cup-plate Method for Antibacterial Test

In this test, we can check the growth of *E. coli* bacteria which induces diarrhea in an individual and the ability of our prebiotic formulation to inhibit the growth of *E. coli* bacteria which means it also can inhibit the induction of *E. coli* induced diarrhea model.

In Plate A, where only the *E. coli* bacteria and agar medium are present, there is uniform bacterial growth, indicating no inhibition. This serves as a control plate to confirm that the bacteria can grow uninhibited in the absence of the prebiotic formulation. In Plate B, zones of inhibition are clearly visible around the wells where the prebiotic formulation was applied. These zones indicate that the formulation is capable of suppressing or inhibiting the growth of *E. coli*. The varying sizes of the inhibition zones suggest that the antibacterial activity might be concentration-dependent, with larger zones correlating to higher concentrations of the formulation.

This outcome supports the hypothesis that the prebiotic formulation possesses antimicrobial as well as antidiarrheal properties. Such activity could be due to the formulation altering the gut microbiota in a way that disfavours *E. coli* proliferation or directly exerting antimicrobial effects.

According to these results, we can say that our prebiotic formulation can inhibit the growth of *E. coli* bacteria by forming a zone of inhibition. As it inhibits a growth of bacteria, we can also say that it

inhibits a diarrhea induced by *E. coli* bacteria. It also works as an antibacterial as well as antidiarrheal agent also. Further, research should be needed to gain more information about this drug in inhibition of *E. coli* induced diarrhea model.

7. DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that PF has antidiarrheal properties, as demonstrated by the 86.11% suppression of defecation at a dosage of 2 ml/rat on comparison with a standard drug. Other trials that demonstrated anti-secretory and anti-motility effects were also conducted.

The present study aimed to evaluate the in-vivo antidiarrheal potential of a novel prebiotic formulation composed of gum acacia, Gir cow ghee, and glucose sugar in a rat model of castor oil-induced diarrhea. The experimental model successfully replicated secretory diarrhea, as evidenced by the prompt onset of diarrhea, increased stool frequency, and the presence of watery feces in the negative control group following castor oil administration. These outcomes are attributed to ricinoleic acid, the active metabolite of castor oil, which irritates the intestinal mucosa, enhances motility, and stimulates prostaglandin release, thereby increasing fluid and electrolyte secretion into the intestinal lumen.

Table 6: Comparison Between Studies

Parameter	Current Study (GA + Gir Cow Ghee + Sugar)	Previous studies on GA alone
Model	Castor oil-induced diarrhea in rats	Castor oil-induced diarrhea in rats
Treatment	Combination of Gum Acacia (GA), Gir cow ghee and Sugar (Prebiotic Formulation)	GA alone
Dose	1ml and 2ml	Typically, 100-500 mg/kg
Onset of Diarrhea	Significantly delayed at 2ml dose	Delayed onset seen in 200-500 mg/kg doses but earlier than our prebiotic formulation
Total fecal output and wet stools	Marked reduction comparable to loperamide at high dose	Reduction observed, but not always comparable to standard

Mechanism proposed	Combined prebiotic, mucosal protection, anti-inflammatory (butyrate), electrolyte reabsorption	Prebiotic effect, anti-secretory, mucosal coating
Additional benefits	Gir cow ghee (butyrate source), Sugar (sodium-glucose co-transport, water reabsorption) enhanced effects	Limited to GA's fiber and prebiotic properties
Safety profile	No observed toxicity	Consistently shown to be safe and well tolerated

At every tested dosage, the PF effectively reduced the peristaltic activity caused by castor oil. The maximum dosage of PF has a peristaltic inhibitory activity that is nearly identical to that of loperamide. In a mouse model, PF demonstrated strong anti-diarrheal efficacy, most likely due to antisecretory and antimotility properties. The prebiotic formulation's multifaceted target strategy may have made this dual mechanism viable.

The cup plate method used in this experiment provides a clear qualitative indication of the antimicrobial activity of the prebiotic formulation against *E. coli*. In Plate A, where only the *E. coli* bacteria and agar medium are present, there is uniform bacterial growth, indicating no inhibition. This plate serves as a control plate to confirm the bacterial growth.

In Plate B, zones of inhibition are clearly visible around the cups in a cup-plate method where the prebiotic formulation was applied. These zones indicate that the formulation is capable of suppressing the growth of *E. coli* bacteria by forming a zone of inhibition. The varying sizes of the inhibition zones suggest that the antibacterial activity might be concentration-dependent, with larger zones correlating to higher concentrations of the formulation.

This outcome supports the hypothesis that the prebiotic formulation possesses antimicrobial properties. Such activity could be due to the formulation altering the gut microbiota in a way that disfavours *E. coli* proliferation or directly exerting antimicrobial effect.

The current study aligns with and extends previous findings that support the antidiarrheal properties of

Gum Acacia (GA) in castor-oil induced diarrhea models. Various earlier investigations have demonstrated the beneficial effect of GA on gastrointestinal health, particularly in regulating stool consistency, enhancing water and electrolyte absorption and modulating gut microbiota.

So, from all these results it can show that our prebiotic formulation can work as an antidiarrheal agent in both castor oil-induced model as well as *E. coli*-induced model.

8. CONCLUSION

The study evaluated a novel prebiotic formulation (PF) consisting of Gum Acacia, Gir cow ghee, and sugar for its antidiarrheal potential using a rat model. The PF showed significant efficacy, particularly at a dose of 2 ml/rat, with an 86.11% reduction in defecation, comparable to loperamide. Unlike previous studies using Gum Acacia alone, which offered modest benefits, the formulation exhibited enhanced effects at lower doses due to the synergistic actions of its components: Gum Acacia modulates gut microbiota; Gir cow ghee provides mucosal protection; and sugar aids in hydration. Antimicrobial tests indicated that the PF effectively inhibited *E. coli*, suggesting potential protective effects against bacterial diarrhea. No adverse effects were observed, affirming its safety. The findings support the PF as a natural alternative to conventional antidiarrheal agents and indicate its efficacy against both castor oil-induced and *E. coli*-induced diarrhea. Further investigation into its pharmacodynamics is advised.

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